

Alsultani Rules to Find the Particular Solution of Ricatti's Equation

Abdulhussein Kadhum Alsultani
Retired Mechanical Engineer
Baghdad , Iraq

Abstract:- Returning to the general Ricatti equation, we see that we can construct the general solution if a particular solution is known .Unfortunately , there is no strict algorithm to find the particular solution , which depends on the types of the functions $A(x)$, $B(x)$, and $C(x)$, When I had studied Ricatti's equation I found that several attempts were made to find the particular solution of some types of equations but there is no guides to solve all the types of ricatti equation .

Keyword:- Ricatti Equation ,Particular Solution ,Alsultani Rules to find Rules to find the Particular Solution of Ricatti's Equation

I. INTRODUCTION

Generally Ricatti equation is:

$$y' = A(x)y^2 + B(x)y + C(x). \text{ , and } (y_1) \text{ is a given particular solution . [1]} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where $A(x)$, $B(x)$ and $C(x)$ are functions of (x) .

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + (2Ay_1 + B)y = -A \quad \text{Alsultani D.E. 2 [4]} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

From Eq. (2) we see that the function $C(x)$ didn't inter in the differential equation but when it equals zero then the equation may be Bernoulli's equation or any other type which consists of three terms , so solved directly without needing to the particular solution so for this reason I say that there is a relationship must be between (y_1) and $C(x)$ only .

From Ricatti equation we see that ;

$$y' = A(x)y^2 + B(x)y + C(x). \text{ , and } (y_1) \text{ is a given particular solution}$$

now if $y' = 0$ this means that the integration of it is $\int y' dx = y = c$ (constant)

and this will affect on the right side of the equation and makes it as a function and not a derivative so $y' \neq 0$

$$y' = A(x)y^2 + B(x)y + C(x) \quad \text{Ricatti equation .}$$

After I studied many Ricatti's equations I find that the particular solution of any one of them can be solved by one of the seven Rules which I put .

Below the disprections of seven Rules to find the Particular Solution (y_1) which produced from Eq.(1) easily with their applications ;

If Ricatti equation is in it's general form (consists of four terms) then we can arrange it by transforming $B(x)y$ from the right side to the left as follow ;

$$y' = A(x)y^2 + B(x)y + C(x) \text{ by arranging it ;}$$

$y' - B(x)y = A(x)y^2 + C(x)$ (here we can consider this arrangement as a trick and we can do the solution directly without it)

So let $C(x) = cK(x)$ where (c) is constant and $K(x)$ is a an absolute function of (x) .

$$\text{Then } y' - B(x)y = A(x)y^2 + c K(x)$$

Since Ricatti’s equation is quadratic then the right side of it is quadratic also because of the existence of (y^2) so we can apply our Rules as follow ;

The right side is $y^2 + cK(x)$

➤ *Rule 1*

if (y^2) has an opposite sign of $cK(x)$ and $c = \mp 1$ or ∓ 4 (their square roots are integer numbers) Then the equation represents the difference between two squares .

so at the point (y_1) and where $A(x)=1$ then

$$y_1^2 = cK(x) \text{ so } y_1 = \pm\sqrt{|cK(x)|} = \pm\sqrt{|C(x)|} \text{ directly}$$

The above two results (\mp) are equal in the magnitude and opposite in the sign

• *Example 1*

$$y' = -x + \frac{1}{2x}y + y^2$$

So $C(x) = cK(x) = -x$ (opposite sign of y^2 , $c = -1$) then $y_1 = \sqrt{|C(x)|} = \pm\sqrt{|-x|} = \mp\sqrt{x}$

$$y_1 = \sqrt{x} \text{ and } y_1' = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}}$$

then to check

$$y' = -x + \frac{1}{2x}y + y^2$$

$$\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} = -x + \frac{1}{2x}(\sqrt{x}) + (\sqrt{x})^2 = -x + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} + x = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} \text{ ok}$$

Also if $y_1 = -\sqrt{x}$ then $y_1' = \frac{-1}{2\sqrt{x}}$

$$y' = -x + \frac{1}{2x}y + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}}$$

$$\frac{-1}{2\sqrt{x}} = -x + \frac{1}{2x}(-\sqrt{x}) + (-\sqrt{x})^2 = -x - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} + x = \frac{-1}{2\sqrt{x}} \text{ ok}$$

➤ *Note*

Here also and from the left side

$$y' - \frac{1}{2x}y = -x + y^2 \text{ we can find the integrating factor } = e^{\int \frac{-dx}{2x}} = e^{\frac{-1}{2}\ln|x|} = \sqrt{x}$$

• *Example 2*

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{-4}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x}y + y^2$$

✓ *Solution*

$C(x) = \frac{-4}{x^2} = y^2$ i.e. $c = -4$ (opposite sign of y^2)

and at point (y_1) we get that $y_1^2 = \frac{-4}{x^2}$ then $y_1 = \pm\sqrt{|C(x)|} = \pm\sqrt{|\frac{-4}{x^2}|} = \mp\frac{2}{x}$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{1}{x}y = y^2 - \frac{4}{x^2} \text{ so at point } y_1 = \frac{2}{x} \text{ and } y_1' = \frac{-2}{x^2}$$

So to check the result

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{-4}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x}y + y^2$$

$$\frac{-2}{x^2} = \frac{-4}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x}\left(\frac{2}{x}\right) + \left(\frac{2}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{-4}{x^2} - \frac{2}{x^2} + \frac{4}{x^2} = \frac{-2}{x^2} \quad ok$$

Now if $y_1 = \frac{-2}{x}$ so $y_1' = \frac{2}{x^2}$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{-4}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x}y + y^2$$

$$\frac{2}{x^2} = \frac{-4}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x}\left(\frac{-2}{x}\right) + \left(\frac{-2}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{-4}{x^2} + \frac{2}{x^2} + \frac{4}{x^2} = \frac{2}{x^2} \quad ok$$

➤ Rule 2

if $C(x) = c K(x)$ and $c = \pm 2$ or ± 3 and they have opposite signs of (y^2) then the equation can be solved as follow ;

at the point (y_1) we find that the particular solution $(y_1) = c\sqrt{K(x)}$

and there is another solution $y_1 = \sqrt{K(x)}$ but with opposite sign of that of (c) ,

so we have two results but they are unequal in their magnitudes and have opposite signs .

• Example 3

$$x^2y' = x^2y^2 + xy - 3$$

✓ Solution

Divide by (x^2)

$$y' = y^2 + \frac{1}{x}y - \frac{3}{x^2} \text{ (also } c \text{ has opposite sign of } y^2)$$

Here $C(x) = \frac{-3}{x^2} = c K(x)$ i.e. $c = -3$ and $K(x) = \frac{1}{x^2}$

so either $y = -3\sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}} = \frac{-3}{x}$ or $y = +\sqrt{K(x)} = +\sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}} = \frac{1}{x}$

Then at point (y_1) we get $y_1^2 = \frac{-3}{x^2}$ so $y_1 = c\sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}} = \frac{-3}{x}$

If we take $y_1 = \frac{-3}{x}$ then $y_1' = \frac{3}{x^2}$

To check

$$y' = y^2 + \frac{1}{x}y - \frac{3}{x^2}$$

$$\frac{3}{x^2} = \left(\frac{-3}{x}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{x}\left(\frac{-3}{x}\right) - \frac{3}{x^2} = \frac{9}{x^2} - \frac{3}{x^2} - \frac{3}{x^2} = \frac{3}{x^2} \quad ok$$

Now if we take $\frac{1}{x} = y_1$ then $y_1' = \frac{-1}{x^2}$

$$\frac{-1}{x^2} = \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{x}\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) - \frac{3}{x^2} = \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^2} - \frac{3}{x^2} = \frac{-1}{x^2} \quad ok$$

➤ Rule 3

If y^2 has the same sign of $cK(x)$ then the equation $y^2 + cK(x)$ represents the summation of two squares and it's unique solution is $y_1 = +\sqrt{|K(x)|}$

• *Example 4*

$$y' - \frac{1}{x}y + y^2 = -\frac{1}{x^2}$$

✓ *Solution*

$y' - \frac{1}{x}y = -\frac{1}{x^2} - y^2$ so they have the same signs (-ve) .

Then $K = \left(\frac{1}{x^2}\right)$ so $y_1 = +\sqrt{K(x)} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}}$ and $y_1' = \frac{-1}{x^2}$

Then to check

$$y' - \frac{1}{x}y + y^2 = -\frac{1}{x^2}$$

$$-\frac{1}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x}\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{-2}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^2} = -\frac{1}{x^2} \quad \text{ok}$$

If we check $y_1 = -\frac{1}{x}$ so it will false

➤ *Rule 4*

If y' is multiplied (x^3) or $x(x^3 \mp \dots)$ then the solution will be

$$y_1 = \sqrt{K(x)} = +\sqrt{x^4} = cx^2 \quad \text{or} \quad y_1 = +\sqrt{K(x)} = +\sqrt{x^4} = +x^2$$

• *Example 5*

$$x(1 - x^3)y' = x^2 + y - 2xy^2$$

✓ *Solution*

Here there is exception because y' is multiplied by x^4

$$\text{so } y_1 = \sqrt{x^4} = x^2 \text{ and } y_1' = 2x$$

to check

$$x(1 - x^3)y' = x^2 + y - 2xy^2$$

$$x(1 - x^3)(2x) = x^2 + x^2 - 2x(x^2)^2$$

$$2x^2 - 2x^5 = 2x^2 - 2x^5 \quad \text{ok}$$

• *Example 6*

$$y' + \frac{1}{x}y - \frac{1}{x^3}y^2 = 2x$$

✓ *Solution*

Multiply the equation by (x^3) and arrange it

$$x^3y' = 2x^4 - x^2y + y^2 \quad \text{then } C(x) = 2x^4 \text{ i.e. } c = 2 \text{ and } K(x) = x^4$$

So $y_1 = \sqrt{x^4} = x^2$ (only + ve sign because c and y^2 have the same signs)

$$\text{then } y_1' = 2x$$

To check it

$$y' + \frac{1}{x}y - \frac{1}{x^3}y^2 = 2x$$

$$2x + \frac{1}{x}(x^2) - \frac{1}{x^3}(x^2)^2 = 2x + x - x = 2x \quad \text{ok}$$

$$\text{Or } y_1 = cK(x) = 2x^2 \quad \text{so } y_1' = 4x$$

To check

$$y' + \frac{1}{x}y - \frac{1}{x^3}y^2 = 2x$$

$$4x + \frac{1}{x}(2x^2) - \frac{1}{x^3}(2x^2)^2 = 2x + 4x - 4x = 2x$$

The old solution

We convert this equation into into the standard form ;

$$x^3y' = 2x^4 - x^2y + y^2$$

As you can see ,we have a Ricatti equation . Tryto find a particular solutionin the form $y_1 = x^2$. Substituting this into Ricatti equation , we can determine the coefficient cc

$$(cx^2)' + \frac{cx^2}{x} - \frac{(cx^2)^2}{x^3} = 2x \rightarrow 2cx + cx - c^2x = 2x, \rightarrow c^2 - 3c + 2 = 0$$

Solving this quadratic equation, we obtain the value of c ;

$$D = 9 - 4 \times 2 = 1. \rightarrow c_{1,2} = \frac{3 \pm \sqrt{1}}{2} = 1, 2$$

Thus, there are even two particular solutions . However , we needonly one of them.
So we take , for example , $y_1 = x^2$

➤ *Rule 5*

$$y' = A(x)y^2 + B(x)y + C(x) \quad \text{and } C(x) \text{ consists of many terms}$$

$$\text{so } y_1 = \pm \sqrt{x \text{ (here } x \text{ has the largest even exponent)}}$$
 only when C(x) and y^2

have opposite signs otherwise only (+ve)

• *Example 7*

$$y' = y^2 - (2x - 1)y + x^2 - x + 1$$

✓ *Solution*

$$C(x) = x^2 - x + 1 \text{ so } y_1 = \sqrt{x^2} = x \text{ so } y_1' = 1 \text{ (only one solution because } y^2 \text{ and } x^2 \text{ have the same signs)}$$

To check the result

$$y' = y^2 - (2x - 1)y + x^2 - x + 1$$

$$1 = x^2 - (2x - 1)x + x^2 - x + 1 = x^2 - 2x^2 + x + x^2 - x + 1 = 1 \quad \text{ok}$$

• *Example 8*

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = y^2 - 2e^xy + e^{2x} + e^x$$

✓ *Solution*

$$C(x) = e^{2x} + e^x \quad \text{so} \quad y_1 = \sqrt{e^{2x}} = e^x \quad \text{and} \quad y_1' = e^x \quad (\text{one solution})$$

To check

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = y^2 - 2e^x y + e^{2x} + e^x$$

$$e^x = (e^x)^2 - 2e^x(e^x) + e^{2x} + e^x = e^{2x} - 2e^{2x} + e^{2x} + e^x = e^x \quad \text{ok}$$

➤ *Rule 6*

$y' \neq 0$ but after the substitution by (y_1) the right side becomes $= 0$ then we must find another magnitude of y_1 .

• *Example 9*

$$y' = (y - x)^2$$

✓ *Solution*

$$y' = (y - x)^2 = y^2 - 2xy + x^2$$

Here $C(x) = x^2$ then $y_1 = \sqrt{x^2} = x$ so $y_1' = 1$

To check the result

$$y' = (y - x)^2$$

$$1 = (x - x)^2 = 0 \neq 1 \quad \text{so to make the result of the right side equal (1)}$$

we choose $y_1 = x + 1$ then $y_1' = 1$ (one solution)

to check the result

$$y' = (y - x)^2$$

$$1 = (x + 1 - x)^2 = 1 \quad \text{ok}$$

➤ *Rule 7*

$$y' = A(x)y^2 + B(x)y + C(x)$$

But if $B(x) = 0$

Then $y' = A(x)y^2 + C(x)$ so $C(x) = cK(x)$ and $y_1 = c\sqrt{|K(x)|}$

and the other solution is $y_1 = \sqrt{K(x)}$ with the opposite sign of $(c)\sqrt{K(x)}$

• *Example 10*

$$y' + y^2 = \frac{2}{x^2}$$

✓ *Solution*

$$y' + y^2 = \frac{2}{x^2} \quad \text{so} \quad C(x) = \frac{2}{x^2} = cK(x) \quad \text{then} \quad c = 2 \quad \text{and} \quad K(x) = \frac{1}{x^2}$$

$$\text{So} \quad y_1 = c\sqrt{|K(x)|} = 2\sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}} = \frac{2}{x} \quad \text{and} \quad y_1' = \frac{-2}{x^2}$$

To check

$$y' + y^2 = \frac{2}{x^2}$$

$$\frac{-2}{x^2} + \left(\frac{2}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{-2}{x^2} + \frac{4}{x^2} = \frac{2}{x^2} \quad \text{ok}$$

Or $y_1 = \sqrt{K(x)}$ with the opposite sign of $(c)\sqrt{K(x)}$ i.e. $= -\sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}} = -\frac{1}{x}$ so $y_1' = \frac{1}{x^2}$

Then to check the result

$$y' + y^2 = \frac{2}{x^2}$$

$$\frac{1}{x^2} + \left(\frac{-1}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^2} = \frac{2}{x^2} \quad \text{ok}$$

➤ Note

We can solve the last example as follow ;

Suppose that $y = \frac{a}{x}$ so $y' = \frac{-a}{x^2}$ where $a = \text{constant}$

So

$$y' + y^2 = \frac{2}{x^2}$$

$$\frac{-a}{x^2} + \left(\frac{a}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{2}{x^2} \text{ then } a^2 - a - 2 = 0$$

So $(a-2)(a+1) = 0$ then either $a=2$ or $a=-1$

II. MAIN RESULTS

Find the particular solution of the following Riccati equations and solve them .

1)

$$x(x^2 - 1)y' + x^2 - (x^2 - 1)y - y^2 = 0$$

✓ Solution

Using Rule 5

$C(x) = x^2$ then $y_1 = \sqrt{x^2} = +x$ so $y_1' = 1$

Now to check

$$x(x^2 - 1)y' + x^2 - (x^2 - 1)y - y^2 = 0$$

$$x(x^2 - 1)(1) + x^2 - (x^2 - 1)(x) - (x)^2 = 0$$

$$x^3 - x + x^2 - x^3 + x - x^2 = 0 \quad \text{ok}$$

Dividing the problem by $x(x^2 - 1)$ we get

$$y' = \frac{1}{x(x^2 - 1)}y^2 + \frac{x^2 - 1}{x(x^2 - 1)}y - \frac{x^2}{x(x^2 - 1)}$$

Then

$A(x) = \frac{1}{x(x^2 - 1)}$, $B(x) = \frac{1}{x}$ and $C(x) = \frac{-x}{x^2 - 1}$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + (2Ay_1 + B)y = -A \quad (\text{Alsultani D.E. 2}) \quad [4]$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \left[\frac{2 \times 1 \times x}{x(x^2 - 1)} + \frac{1}{x} \right] y = \frac{-1}{x(x^2 - 1)}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \left(\frac{2}{x^2-1} \right) y = - \frac{1}{x(x^2-1)}$$

So $p(x) = \frac{2}{(x^2-1)} + \frac{1}{x}$ so by partial decomposition ;

$$\text{Then } \frac{2}{x^2-1} = \frac{C}{x+1} + \frac{D}{x-1}$$

So $C(x-1)+D(x+1)=2$ then $Cx - C + Dx + D = 2$

$D - C = 2$ and $C + D = 0$ so $D = -C$

$C = -1$ and $D = 1$

$$\text{I.f.} = e^{\int \left(\frac{-1}{x+1} + \frac{1}{x-1} + \frac{1}{x} \right) dx} = e^{\ln x \left(\frac{x-1}{x+1} \right)} = \frac{x(x-1)}{x+1}$$

$$\frac{x(x-1)y}{x+1} = - \int \frac{x(x-1)}{x+1} \times \frac{1}{x(x^2-1)} dx = \int \frac{-dx}{(x+1)^2}$$

Let $x+1 = u$ then $du = dx$

$$\int \frac{-dx}{(x+1)^2} = \int \frac{-du}{u^2} = \frac{1}{u} + c = \frac{1}{x+1} + c = \frac{c(x+1)+1}{x+1}$$

$$\frac{x(x-1)y}{x+1} = \frac{c(x+1)+1}{x+1}$$

$$y = \frac{c(x+1)+1}{x(x-1)} \quad \text{then } \frac{1}{y} = \frac{x(x-1)}{c(x+1)+1}$$

$$y_2 = y_1 + \frac{1}{y} = x + \frac{x(x-1)}{c(x+1)+1} \quad \text{End}$$

2)

$$y' + 7x^{-1}y - 3y^2 = 3x^{-2}$$

✓ *Solution*

$$y' = \frac{3}{x^2} - \frac{7}{x}y + 3y^2$$

➤ *Rule 5*

$\frac{3}{x^2}$ and $3y^2$ have the same signs (+ve) then $y_1 = \sqrt{K(x)} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2}} = \frac{1}{x}$ only

$$y_1' = \frac{-1}{x^2}$$

To check

$$y' = \frac{3}{x^2} - \frac{7}{x}y + 3y^2$$

$$\frac{-1}{x^2} = \frac{3}{x^2} - \frac{7}{x} \left(\frac{1}{x} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{1}{x} \right)^2 = \frac{3}{x^2} - \frac{7}{x^2} + \frac{3}{x^2} = \frac{-1}{x^2} \quad \text{ok}$$

$$A=3, \quad B = \frac{-7}{x} \quad \text{and} \quad C = \frac{3}{x^2}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + (3Ay_1 + B)y = -A$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \left(\frac{2 \times 1 \times 3}{x} - \frac{7}{x}\right)y = -3 \quad \text{so} \quad \frac{dy}{dx} - \frac{1}{x}y = -3$$

Then I.f. = $e^{\int \frac{-dx}{x}} = \frac{1}{x}$

So $\frac{y}{x} = -3 \int \frac{dx}{x} = -3 \ln|x| + c$ then $y = x(c - 3 \ln|x|)$

$$\frac{1}{y} = \frac{1}{x(c-3 \ln x)}$$

$y_2 = y_1 + \frac{1}{y} = \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x(c-3 \ln x)}$ End

3)

$$y' = x^3 + \frac{2}{x}y - \frac{1}{x}y^2$$

Multiply by (x) we get

$$xy' = x^4 + 2y - y^2$$

So $C(x) = x^4$ then $y_1 = \mp \sqrt{|C(x)|} = \mp \sqrt{x^4} = \mp x^2$ (because $C(x)$ and y^2 have opposite signs)

When $y_1 = x^2$ then $y_1' = 2x$

To check

$$y' = x^3 + \frac{2}{x}y - \frac{1}{x}y^2$$

$$2x = x^3 + \frac{2}{x}(x^2) - \frac{1}{x}(x^2)^2 = x^3 + 2x - x^3 = 2x \quad \text{ok}$$

Now $A = \frac{-1}{x}$, $B = \frac{2}{x}$ and $y_1 = x^2$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + (2Ay_1 + B)y = -A$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \left(\frac{-2}{x} \times x^2 + \frac{2}{x}\right)y = \frac{1}{x}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \left(-2x + \frac{2}{x}\right)y = \frac{1}{x}$$

I.f. = $e^{\int (-2x + \frac{2}{x})dx} = x^2 e^{-x^2}$

Let $e^{-x^2} = u$ then $-2xe^{-x^2} dx = du$

$$yx^2 e^{-x^2} = \int \frac{1}{x}(x^2 e^{-x^2})dx = \int xe^{-x^2} dx = -\frac{e^{-x^2}}{2} + c = \frac{2c - e^{-x^2}}{2}$$

Then $y = \frac{2c - e^{-x^2}}{2} \times \frac{1}{x^2 e^{-x^2}} = \frac{2c - e^{-x^2}}{2x^2 e^{-x^2}}$ so $\frac{1}{y} = \frac{2x^2 e^{-x^2}}{2c - e^{-x^2}}$

$$y_2 = y_1 + \frac{1}{y} = x^2 + \frac{2x^2 e^{-x^2}}{2c - e^{-x^2}}$$

also $y_1 = -x^2$ is another answer then $y_1' = -2x$ to check

$$y' = x^3 + \frac{2}{x}y - \frac{1}{x}y^2$$

$$-2x = x^3 + \frac{2}{x}(-x^2) - \frac{1}{x}(-x^2)^2 = x^3 - 2x - x^3 = -2x \quad \text{End}$$

4) $y' + 6y^2 = \frac{1}{x^2}$

✓ *Solution*

$y_2=y^{-1}$ then $y_2' = -\frac{1}{y^2}$ substitute in the problem

$$\frac{dy_2}{dx} = -6y_2^2 + \frac{1}{x^2}$$

$$\frac{dy_2}{dx} + \frac{P(x)}{n}y_2^k = Q(x)y^k \quad [3] \text{ i.e. } k = 2 = 1 - n \text{ so } n = -1$$

$$-\frac{1}{y_2^2} \frac{dy_2}{dx} = -6 \left(\frac{1}{y_2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{x^2} \text{ so multiply by } (-y_2^2) \text{ we get}$$

$$\frac{dy_2}{dx} = -6 + \frac{y_2^2}{x^2} \text{ homogeneous equation then let } y_2=vx \text{ so } dy = vdx+xdv$$

$$\frac{dy_2}{dx} = \frac{xdv+vdx}{dx} = x \frac{dv}{dx} + v = -6 + v^2$$

$$x \frac{dv}{dx} = v^2 - v - 6 \text{ so } \frac{dx}{x} = \frac{dv}{v^2-v-6}$$

and we can solve it by partial decomposition

$$\frac{1}{v^2-v-6} = \frac{A}{v-3} + \frac{B}{v+2}$$

$$A(v+2)+B(v-3)=1 \text{ then } Av+2A+Bv-3B = 1 \text{ so } A+B=0 \text{ and } 2A-3B=1$$

$$\text{Then } A=-B \text{ and } 2A+3A=1 \text{ so } A=\frac{1}{5} \text{ and } B=\frac{-1}{5}$$

$$\frac{dx}{x} = \frac{dv}{5(v-3)} - \frac{dv}{5(v+2)} \text{ so } \ln|x| = \frac{1}{5} \ln \frac{v-3}{v+2} + c$$

$$cx^5 = \frac{v-3}{v+2} \text{ since } v = \frac{y_2}{x} \text{ then } cx^5 = \frac{\frac{y_2}{x}-3}{\frac{y_2}{x}+2} = \frac{y_2+3x}{y_2-2x}$$

$$\text{But } y_2=\frac{1}{y} \text{ then } cx^5 = \frac{\frac{1}{y}-3x}{\frac{1}{y}+2x} = \frac{1-3xy}{1+2xy}$$

III. CONCLUSION

- After reading this research we recognize that $C(x)=cK(x)$ and finding the particular Solution of the problem directly .
- We see that the particular solution is the key of solving Ricatti's equation and so without it the work will become without advantage .
- Before this research so the procedure of finding the particular solution needs a strict algorithm but now it is easy to find it and may be with more than one result as we saw .
- Although I put seven Rules but they are simple and we can keep them in our mind quickly .
- By these Rules and my differential equation [Alsultani D.E.2] [3] then the solutions of Ricatti's differential equations will be faster and without the complicated substitutions.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ricatti Jacope (1724) 'Animadversiones inaequaiones differentials secunde Gradus'(Observations regarding differential equations of the second order), Actorum Eruditorum, quae Lipsiae publicantur .Supplementa, 8: 66- y3. Translation Of the original Latin into English by Ian Bruce .
- [2]. Ince. E. L.(1956) [1926] Ordinary Differential Equations, New York: Dover Publications, pp. 23-25
- [3]. <https://ijisrt.com/new-method-to-solve-the-first-order-de-which-consists-of-three-terms>
- [4]. <https://ijisrt.com/fast-way-to-solve-ricatti-equation>.